

Life Cycle Assessment on Denim: Focus on the Indian Consumer's Phase

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Abstract:

Denim has established itself as a prominent presence in the fashion industry, serving as an essential component in various clothing styles, ranging from formal attire to casual wear. India's domestic denim industry is experiencing significant growth, leading to intense competition in the international denim market. This study primarily investigates the life cycle assessment of denim garments, with a specific focus on energy and water consumption during the consumer phase. The analysis encompasses three distinct demographics in India: urban, semi-urban, and rural areas. This study investigated the consumer phase hotspots of denim garments among different demographic groups. This study finds that the consumer phase of the life cycle has the greatest climate change impact, primarily due to the consumption of non-renewable resources. Specifically, urban consumers in India are found to contribute more significantly to climate change through practices such as drying and ironing, while rural consumers tend to use fewer non-renewable energy sources for these activities. Hence, this study enables the identification of potential changes in the Indian denim consumer phase. Urban consumers tend to consume a greater amount of water and energy compared to other demographic groups when washing and drying their denim garments. Compared to other nations, a significant proportion of Indian consumers prefer cold-cold washing methods. This study helps identify hotspots, enabling actions to reduce environmental impacts in denim production's consumer phase by minimizing energy and water consumption. It also contributes to the attainment of the United Nations sustainability goals (SDGs).

Keywords: denim consumers, domestic laundering, drying, India, LCA, microplastics

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1. Introduction

Over the past two decades, the fashion garment sector has seen profound changes including mass manufacturing, growth in the number of fashion seasons, affordable and fast fashion, rising consumer spending, and other related factors. The Indian retail and fashion industry have seen significant expansion over the past two decades, particularly in the areas of western and casual clothing. Among these, denim is one of the fastest growing in the domestic market with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 14.8% between 2021 and 2027, the Indian fashion industry is expected to rise from its 2021 value of \$151.2 B to \$344.1 B [1]. Worldwide one of the leading segments in apparel fashion is the denim wear segment. For the past decades, one of the most ubiquitous wardrobe essentials is blue denim. Compared to developed countries per capita jeans consumption in India is much lower which indicates a clear scope for growth in the domestic market [2, 3]. The young demographic (15-29) accounts for 26% of the country's consumer base and is the primary growth driver of denim wear [4].

The denim market in India is predicted to grow at a CAGR of 8 to 9% through 2028, reaching Rs. 91,894 crores (~\$12.27 billion) [5]. **Denim is more than simply casual wear for most young Indians [6]. Whereas in India until recently, denim was only widely worn in metropolitan and semi-urban centers. Increases in education and access to information via the Internet have led to its rapid development into hitherto untapped rural sectors [6].** On one side, with very huge market potentials and gaining high profit and income, in a populated country like India, environmental impacts are a very serious issue.

It is crucial to address the mitigation of environmental issues arising from consumer products. Textiles and garments, specifically, make a substantial contribution to the generation of solid and liquid waste [7–10]. Additionally, there is growing concern regarding the emission of microplastics during the consumer phase, primarily resulting from domestic washing and subsequent related processes [11,12]. The utilization of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) has been extensively employed in the evaluation of the environmental impacts associated with the textile industry and various clothing items. Accordingly, it is essential to perform the LCA on the denim to know the true environmental effect, which is guaranteed to raise consumer awareness and ultimately lead to fewer environmental hazards [13–15]. This research has ushered in a new era in our understanding of the environmental impacts of a single pair of jeans among Indian consumers across different demographics, including those in urban, semi-urban, and rural areas.

The most comprehensive approach to assessing the environmental impacts of denim is LCA which is graded by the ISO 14040-14043 industry standard [16–19]. This evaluation was conducted after defining its goal, scope, inventory analysis, conducting an impact assessment, and interpreting the results [20–22]. In the Indian consumer phase, this work provides a conceptual and analytical framework for the LCA of denim. This study was conducted in India concerning demographics including 7 urban, 7 semi-urban, and 7 rural. The average values used to analyze their life cycle assessment, including the global warming potential which is CO₂ equivalents (CO₂-e), water consumption, and energy consumption are described during the consumer use of one pair of jeans. A more systematic and holistic approach to developing strategies to respond to the environmental aspects of sustainable development in the denim industry concerning the consumer phase has been attempted to integrate it. This study mainly focuses on energy and water consumption, specifically the energy and water utilized in the washing, drying processes and ironing process of denim products in their consumer phase with the help of statistical tools. Despite the environmental implications that are involved with the consumer phase of denim goods, there is still a paucity of analysis about the amount of energy and water that is consumed during that phase. It is necessary to develop a system for locating the hotspots and factors that influence the amount of energy and water that is consumed during the consumer phase of denim garments.

2. Materials and Methods

The goal and scope phase establishes the functional unit of analysis, which includes both women's and men's denim (i.e., weighing approximately 350± 50 g), as well as the specific life cycle stages of interest. The study observed a use phase spanning a duration of 6 months. In this assessment, data regarding consumer use behavior was collected from various demographic groups in India through the administration of surveys. The responses from people living in urban and semi-urban areas were collected using a methodology that focused only on the internet, but in rural areas, face-to-face interviews and a system based on paper were used. The questionnaires (supplement) administered were standardized across all three demographic groups, with a sample size of over 500 participants at each location. The survey required respondents to be at least 15+ years old, residing in specific locations, owning at least one pair of denim with respective weights, and have knowledge of both machine and hand washing methods for denim. The present study seeks to offer consumers an initial understanding of the potential environmental effects of denim by examining various impact categories. The following metrics will be discussed: the global warming potential, referred to as carbon footprint, measured in kilograms of CO₂-equivalents (CO₂-eq); the non-renewable energy demand; and the water depletion, measured in water-equivalents (water-eq).

2.1. System Boundaries

The system boundaries of the current study are depicted in Figure 1, specifically referring to the consumer phase. Therefore, the system boundaries exclusively encompass the activities related to home laundering, including washing, drying, and pressing.

Figure 1: System boundary for the current study

2.2 Environmental Impact Categories

The environmental impact potential is expressed at a midpoint and endpoint level. The description of environmental impact categories is shown in Table 1.

Table. 1 Impact categories and descriptions

Category	Description	Units
Climate change	Global warming potential (GWP) of greenhouse gasses released into the environment.	e-CO ₂ emission in kilograms
Water Consumption	Net freshwater taken from the environment minus water returned to the same watershed at the same quality or better.	Liters
Eutrophication	There is no major influence on the consumer phase of the lifecycle of the eutrophication process, but it has a considerable impact on the production phase (i.e., the fiber cultivation stage).	
Land occupation:	The cultivation of fiber is the most intensive use of land in the production of denim.	
Abiotic depletion:	There is no significant impact on the consumer phase of the lifecycle for abiotic depletion.	

3. Results and Discussion

The demographic characteristics of the respondents in each location are representative of the population depicted in Figure 2. In general, female respondents exhibit a 3-7% lower response rate compared to the average response rate of all respondents.

Figure 2 : Male (a,b,c) and female (d,e,f) respondent demographics in India by urban (a&d), semi-urban (b&e), and rural (c&f).

3.1 Washing and wearing frequencies

When conducting a consumer phase LCA for denim, it is crucial to account for the frequency of washes and the overall lifespan of denim garments. The frequency of laundering denim depends on factors such as the number of days it is worn before washing, the duration of use, and the frequency of wearing the garment. This survey specifically inquired about the frequency of laundering a single garment between its usage and overall lifespan. The average number of launderings performed by users from urban, semi-urban, and rural demographics was calculated using the responses for each choice. Rural residents have the lowest frequency of washing their clothing between wearing cycles, with an average of 6.4 washes per cycle (

Figure 3a). In addition, rural residents demonstrated a higher lifetime usage rate compared to urban customers, with approximately double the usage (

Figure 3b). The economic status of rural, metropolitan, and semi-urban customers varies due to differences in their purchasing habits and requirements. Wearing clothes for longer periods of time is a recommended practice in water conservation. This practice reduces water consumption during the consumer phase of the product lifecycle and minimizes the overall environmental impact. There is a need for increased frequency of washing in urban areas.

Figure 3 : Number of washings between wearing frequencies (a) and the denim lifetime (b).

3.2 Washing machine and washing type

It has been established that the activity of domestic washing is a substantial global warming potential (GWP) contribution to their life cycle [23]. According to the findings of the survey, most denim consumers who live in metropolitan areas do their laundry at home using a washing machine. The rate of people washing their hands at home in rural was found to be higher, at 69%. It's possible that the lower rates of machine washing in rural areas are due to long-standing cultural activities, lower levels of discretionary spending, or a smaller quantity of available space in homes for washing machines. However, in recent times the rate of machine washing may rise in the future as Indian rural continue to expand and their lifestyles improve. To get a more in-depth understanding of the washing machine technology that was reported, a study was carried out to determine the type of washing machines that are utilized in the various regions of India. In India, the cost of electricity varies by province and can be averaged. The cost of energy on average in India's cities, towns, and rural in 2022. Customers may be more likely to transition from low-efficiency to high-efficiency washing machines due to increased electricity costs in India and the marketing of Energy Star products, lessening the total environmental impact of the garment washing process.

Figure 5 shows the lifetime water intake for one pair of denim concerning different washing frequencies. In fact, the water intake for washing every time you wear is higher than other frequencies, in this case, urban and semi-urban consumers were consuming more quantity of water (1150 and 980 liters) than rural consumers, whereas they consume 815 liters of water with constant washing and wearing cycle (Figure 5a). Among these, rural consumers have good practices by reducing their water intake as compared to urban and semi-urban consumers.

The temperatures of the water also play an essential role in the laundry process since higher water temperatures need more energy and are considered to have a greater ability to mitigate the effects of climate change. During the survey, each participant was given information regarding two different washing temperatures: one for the washing process, and another for the rinsing process. The survey was constructed with three different washing practice

options, including cold-cold washing, warm-cold washing, and warm-warm washing. It was reported by the average values of the Indian consumer phase that 99.9% of rural consumers in India use the cold-cold washing procedure. This is because of the traditional way of washing practices and living styles and the most important thing is that they do not prefer to use washing machines. **In the meanwhile, 81% of consumers who live in metropolitan areas employ the warm-warm washing process (Figure 5b).** Overall, customers residing in rural lowered the amount of energy required for washing denim. The reason for this is that they use of less washing machines and water that is colder; therefore, this has a substantial impact on reducing the amount of energy consumed.

Figure 4 : Lifetime water consumption for different frequencies of washing between wears (a), washing habits (b).

In general, the lowest number of washing frequencies required higher non-renewable energy, the results proven with numerical values. On average, urban consumers use more energy to wash their denim than others, moreover rural consume less energy as well their washing frequency is less which resulting the lowest amount of energy utilization in the consumer phase of the life cycle. On average, the energy required for 1x washing frequency, urban consumers use 23.1 kWh, semi-urban use 15.4 kWh, and rural consumers 8kWh, which is shown in Figure 5b. On average, the energy required for 1x washing frequency always shows a higher impact on the CO₂ emission, particularly with urban consumers showing the highest CO₂ emission (11.3 kg e-CO₂), it is due to the higher utilization of washing machines as well as the use of warm-cold (i.e., 13% responses) washing procedures. Generally, the climate change impact always depends on the amount of non-renewable energy usage, in this occasion, urban consumers play a vital role in climate change. In all washing frequencies, rural people show fewer carbon emissions (3.2 kg e-CO₂) than urban and semi-urban consumers due to less utilization of washing machines and their living style directly involved in reducing energy consumption (Figure 5b).

Figure 5 : Lifetime non-renewable energy consumption (a), and emission of CO₂ during the consumer phase (b).

3.3 Effect of drying techniques

Drying is an important process which usually carried out after the laundering process, generally, there are two methods of drying, which are line drying (i.e., air drying) and using the machine to dry their denim. However, denim is made through cellulosic fibers (i.e., cotton and lyocell) and it is hygroscopic [24,25], also it is made through coarse counts which results in heavy fabric and absorbs more quantity of water, as a result, denim required more time for the drying process. Normally, the line drying process has many advantages no energy is required, it generally leaves your clothes fresh, mostly it does not require the ironing process and the most important point is environmentally friendly [26]. The only disadvantages of this process are it takes more time to dry the jeans (which may be a few hours to a day or sometimes more particularly in winter). Drying jeans in the line dry is the kind of practice rural people are doing regularly; On average, among this study's data, 88%, 67%, and 54% of the respondents from rural, semi-urban, and urban did not use a machine to dry their denim respectively (

Figure 6-a). Like machine drying, the ironing process also impacts the GWP, as it consumes large energy. 12%, 24%, and 31% of the respondents from rural, semi-urban, and urban use ironing after line drying. Overall, rural consumers do not use the machine to dry and as well as ironing, which reduces their electricity consumption.

Urban consumers use ironing, and machine drying for their denim shows huge carbon emissions (Figure 6b), in this occasion, rural has the very least emission of CO₂ during after washing process. Therefore, the utilization of line drying can reduce the utilization of non-renewable energy also, it reduces the climate impact. So, no doubt that line drying alone can save the environment as compared to other processes, in this point, the fashion brand should provide this information on their garments, and help to create awareness among their consumers. On average, the consumption of non-renewable energy for drying followed by ironing is the highest and always shows higher carbon emissions than other methods.

Figure 6 : Responses of drying and ironing process (a), their equivalent CO₂ emission and energy consumption.

3.4. End of life of denim

More than one million metric tons of textiles are discarded every year in India, with most of this waste coming from household environments [27]. Nevertheless, even the highest-quality denim has a finite lifespan and will need to be replaced at some point. To gain a better understanding of their consumer use behavior and the end state of denim, a survey was carried out. This was done for two reasons: first, the effects of denim's end of life on waste, and second, the possibility of extending denim's lifespan. According to the findings of the survey, the end of life for denim varies by demographic. In response to the survey question, an average of 40.2% of urban residents said that they throw away their denim once it has reached the end of its life. In addition, 22% of urban residents said that they retain denim in their wardrobe (Figure 6). It is interesting to learn that consumers in rural areas reuse their denim in a variety of ways, such as a pillow cover, as stuffing materials for their mattress, as curtains, as cleaning cloth, and as a raw material for making threads to use in some domestic applications. However, consumers of all three demographic groups keep their old denim in their wardrobes, and because almost the same percentage of

respondents from each group was collected, this research will focus on helping those demographic groups comprehend the significance of engaging in environmentally responsible shopping practices.

Figure 7 : Responses of end of life of denim consumer’s behavior in India.

Recycling denim is the only method to boost their circular economy, and several denim brands are inventing creative techniques for recycling old denim into new denim clothes. These brands include captions such as “we want your jeans back” to encourage consumers to return their jeans, also they provide discounts that the customers can use to buy new garments. The concept of second-hand clothing stores is not very well known in India; however, this is expected to change in the coming years. In these stores, denim can be given additional lives, which not only helps cut down on the overall waste that is associated with clothing but also helps cut down on the impacts that garment production has over the journey of a product’s lifetime. Overall, recycling, provides important environmental benefits, like it

- Reduces the need for landfill.
- Reduces pressure on virgin resources (i.e., cotton cultivation, etc.).
- Results in less pollution load, and energy savings.

Moreover, the consumer phase of any garments was responsible for another global threat known as microplastics (i.e., garments made from synthetic fibers) and microfibers (i.e., a garment made from natural fibers). It was determined that one of the key sources of microplastic contamination is created in the washing of textiles and garments. It is anticipated that the presence of microplastic pollution will increase to a greater extent as the human population will continue to grow and as people will continue to wash their garments more frequently [28–32]. **Regrettably, denim is also one of the most significant contributors to microplastic emissions, according to the findings of the most current research, the denim fabric that was produced with 97% PET and 3% Lycra was discovered to contain an average of 2300000-4900000 microfibers per 1-kilogram wash load [23]. It confirms that each washing is the most responsible for the release of microplastics, the best way to reduce the microplastic releases could be to decrease the washing frequency, and however, there is no evidence for this statement [33-34].**

4. Conclusion

The average washing, pressing, and drying frequencies concerning different demographics. Overall, urban consumers use more water and energy to wash and dry their denim than consumers in the other demography. One interesting finding is that most Indian consumers use cold-cold washing procedures as compared to other nations [3]. From this study, the consumer phase of the life cycle shows the highest impact of climate change due to the number of processes that consumes non-renewable resources, on average urban consumers from India are more responsible for climate change due to the drying, ironing habits, and other related practices, whereas, rural consumers use very less non-renewable energy (warm water, drying, ironing), therefore it reduces the carbon

footprint. On the other hand, the urban consumers utilized the highest water consumption (i.e., 1150 liters for their entire lifetime), which is very high as compared to the rural consumers (i.e., 815 liters). Wearing jeans 10 times before washing has a significant influence on water consumption, as a result, denim users are recommended to use this strategy, which will have a significant global climate effect. There is no major influence on the consumer phase of the lifecycle of eutrophication, abiotic process, and land consumption.

i. Data availability

All data generated during this study are available to the corresponding author upon the request.

ii. Conflict of interest

No funding was received to assist with the preparation of this manuscript. The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

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